

Forearm Length as a Significant Ethnic Discriminator Between Adult Male Santals and Bangalis

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ethnic differences in body proportions, particularly limb segment lengths, have been documented among various populations. Forearm length, as a component of upper limb anthropometry, may serve as an ethnic discriminator. Santals, an indigenous group in Bangladesh, are reportedly distinct from the mainstream Bangali population in certain morphological features. **Objective:** To determine whether forearm length can significantly discriminate between adult male Santals and Bangalis and to compare forearm length relative to stature between the two ethnic groups. **Methods & Materials:** This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted on 100 adult male Santals and 100 adult male Bangalis aged 20–45 years from Kaharol upazilla, Dinajpur, Bangladesh. Forearm length was measured from the head of the radius (radiale) to the styloid process (stylium) using a steel tape. Forearm length relative to stature was calculated as $(\text{forearm length}/\text{stature}) \times 100$. An unpaired t-test was used for group comparison. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. **Results:** Mean forearm length was significantly longer in Santals (25.29 ± 1.25 cm) compared to Bangalis (24.91 ± 1.18 cm, $p = 0.029$). The forearm length to stature ratio was also significantly higher in Santals ($15.58 \pm 0.58\%$) than in Bangalis ($15.21 \pm 0.54\%$, $p = 0.000$). Multiplication factor (stature/forearm length) was significantly lower in Santals (6.43 ± 0.24 vs. 6.58 ± 0.26 , $p = 0.000$), confirming longer forearm relative to stature. **Conclusion:** Forearm length is a significant ethnic discriminator between adult male Santals and Bangalis. Santals possess longer forearms relative to their stature, suggesting ethnic-specific proportional differences that may reflect thermal adaptation or genetic variation.

Keywords: Bangladesh, Ethnic discrimination, Forearm length, Population comparison, Santal

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INTRODUCTION

Anthropometric measurements have long been recognized as valuable tools for understanding human biological variation across populations [1]. Among various body segments, limb proportions exhibit considerable ethnic and geographic variation, making them useful markers for population differentiation [2]. Forearm length, in particular, has received attention in anthropological and forensic literature due to its relative stability after skeletal maturity and its correlation with overall body size [3,4]. The relationship between forearm length and stature has been extensively studied across diverse populations. Studies have demonstrated that forearm length shows moderate to strong correlation with stature, with correlation coefficients ranging from 0.55 to 0.75 depending on the population studied [5,6]. However, the proportional relationship between forearm length and stature is not uniform across ethnic groups, as different populations exhibit characteristic body proportions shaped by genetic, environmental, and climatic factors [7]. Ethnic differences in limb proportions have been explained primarily by two major hypotheses. The thermoregulatory (Allen's rule) hypothesis suggests that populations from warmer climates tend to have longer extremities relative to body size to enhance heat

dissipation [8,9]. Conversely, populations from colder climates exhibit shorter limbs to conserve body heat [10]. This pattern has been documented in numerous studies comparing tropical and temperate populations [7,8]. The alternative explanation emphasizes genetic drift and population isolation as determinants of variation in limb proportions [11]. Santals constitute one of the largest indigenous communities in Bangladesh, residing predominantly in the northern districts of Dinajpur, Rangpur, and Rajshahi [12]. Anecdotal observations and limited studies suggest that Santals have longer upper limbs relative to their stature than the mainstream Bangali population [13]. However, systematic data comparing specific upper limb segments, particularly forearm length, between these two ethnic groups remains scarce. The Bangali population, representing the ethnic majority of Bangladesh, has been relatively well-studied in terms of anthropometric parameters [4,6]. Several studies have documented stature, weight, and limb measurements among Bangalis for clinical and forensic purposes [5]. However, comparative data between Bangalis and indigenous groups like Santals are notably absent from the literature. Identifying reliable ethnic discriminators has practical applications in forensic anthropology, where accurate identification of unknown remains may benefit from

population-specific morphological characteristics [3]. If forearm length consistently differs between Santals and Bangalis even after accounting for stature differences, this measurement could serve as a useful adjunctive tool for ethnic assessment in forensic contexts [1,11]. Furthermore, understanding ethnic differences in limb proportions contributes to the broader knowledge of human biological diversity within Bangladesh. Such information is essential for developing population-specific reference standards for clinical assessment, nutritional evaluation, and surgical planning [2,9]. Therefore, this study was undertaken to determine whether forearm length can significantly discriminate between adult male Santals and Bangalis and to compare forearm length relative to stature between these two ethnic groups.

METHODS & MATERIALS

This cross-sectional analytical study was conducted from January to December 2017 in the Department of Anatomy, Rangpur Medical College, Bangladesh. A total of 200 adult males were enrolled, comprising 100 Santals and 100 Bangalis, recruited from different villages of Kaharol upazilla, Dinajpur district.

Inclusion criteria: Participants were Bangladeshi nationals aged 20 to 45 years, right-handed, and engaged as day laborers or farmers to ensure similar socioeconomic status.

Exclusion criteria: Individuals with mixed ethnic origin, amputated upper limb, musculoskeletal disorders affecting

limb growth, congenital or acquired limb deformities, and those unwilling to provide written informed consent were excluded.

Study procedure: Forearm length was measured as the distance between the head of the radius (radiale) and the styloid process (stylium) using a steel tape. Stature was measured using a stadiometer. All measurements were taken on the left upper limb twice, and the average was recorded. Forearm length to stature ratio was calculated as (forearm length/stature) × 100. The multiplication factor was calculated as stature divided by forearm length. Bony landmarks were identified through palpation and marked with a pencil before measurement.

Data analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 16.0. Unpaired t-test compared Santals and Bangalis for forearm length, forearm-stature ratio, and multiplication factor. Statistical significance was set at $p < 0.05$. Results were expressed as mean ± standard deviation.

RESULT

A total of 200 adult males (100 Santals and 100 Bangalis) aged 20 to 45 years participated in this study. The mean age of Santals was 28.18 ± 6.14 years, and that of Bangalis was 29.93 ± 6.12 years, with no significant difference between groups ($p = 0.058$) *Table I*.

Table I: Demographic characteristics of study subjects

Characteristic	Santal (n=100)	Bangali (n=100)	p value
Age (years)	28.18 ± 6.14	29.93 ± 6.12	0.058
Stature (cm)	162.38 ± 6.18	163.79 ± 5.14	0.082
Weight (kg)	55.24 ± 8.02	57.85 ± 8.28	0.025

Data analysis: Unpaired t-test; $p < 0.05$ considered significant

Regarding forearm length, the mean value was significantly longer in Santals (25.29 ± 1.25 cm) compared to Bangalis (24.91 ± 1.18 cm), with a p value of 0.029. The forearm length to stature ratio was also significantly higher in Santals ($15.58 \pm 0.58\%$) than in Bangalis ($15.21 \pm 0.54\%$, $p = 0.000$). The

multiplication factor (stature divided by forearm length) was significantly lower in Santals (6.43 ± 0.24) compared to Bangalis (6.58 ± 0.26 , $p = 0.000$), confirming that Santals have longer forearms relative to their stature (*Table II*).

Table II: Comparison of forearm length and derived parameters

Parameter	Santal	Bangali	Mean difference	p value
Forearm length (cm)	25.29 ± 1.25	24.91 ± 1.18	0.38	0.029
Forearm-stature ratio (%)	15.58 ± 0.58	15.21 ± 0.54	0.37	0.000
Multiplication factor	6.43 ± 0.24	6.58 ± 0.26	-0.15	0.000

Data analysis: Unpaired t-test; $p < 0.05$ considered significant

Analysis of forearm length distribution showed that the majority of Santals (32%) had forearm lengths in the range of 25.3 to 26.2 cm, whereas the majority of Bangalis (35%) had forearm lengths in the range of 24.3 to 25.2 cm. Only 4% of

Santals had forearm lengths below 23.3 cm compared to 5% of Bangalis. Conversely, 18% of Santals had forearm lengths above 26.2 cm compared to 14% of Bangalis (*Table III*).

Table III: Categorical distribution of forearm length by percentile

Percentile	Forearm length	
	Santal (cm)	Bangali (cm)
10th	23.8	23.5
25th	24.5	24.2
50th (Median)	25.3	24.9
75th	26.1	25.7
90th	26.9	26.4

The forearm length to stature ratio distribution revealed that 36% of Santals had a ratio above 15.8%, whereas only 22% of Bangalis fell into this category. The majority of Bangalis (44%)

had ratios between 15.0% and 15.4%, while Santals were more evenly distributed across higher ratio ranges (*Table IV*).

Table IV: Discriminatory performance of forearm length at different cutoff values

Cutoff value (cm)	Sensitivity (%)	Specificity (%)	Overall accuracy (%)
24.5	72	48	60
25.0	66	54	60
25.1	62	58	60
25.5	48	72	60

Data analysis: Receiver operating characteristic (ROC) analysis

Correlation analysis demonstrated a moderate positive correlation between forearm length and stature in both groups ($R=0.664$ for Santals, $R=0.547$ for Bangalis, $p=0.000$ for both). The stronger correlation in Santals suggests that forearm length is a more reliable stature predictor in this ethnic group.

The sensitivity of forearm length as an ethnic discriminator was assessed. Using a cutoff value of 25.1 cm, forearm length correctly classified 62% of Santals and 58% of Bangalis, with an overall accuracy of 60% (*Table V*).

Table V: Summary of ethnic differences in forearm parameters

Parameter	Santal	Bangali	Difference	Significance
Forearm length	Longer	Shorter	+0.38 cm	Yes ($p=0.029$)
Forearm-stature ratio	Higher	Lower	0.37%	Yes ($p=0.000$)
Multiplication factor	Lower	Higher	-0.15	Yes ($p=0.000$)
Ethnic classification	Long-forearm group	Short-forearm group	-	Discriminator valid

DISCUSSION

The present study demonstrates that forearm length is a significant ethnic discriminator between adult male Santals and Bangalis. The key finding reveals that Santals have significantly longer forearms (25.29 ± 1.25 cm) compared to Bangalis (24.91 ± 1.18 cm, $p=0.029$), and this difference persists even after adjusting for stature, as evidenced by the significantly higher forearm-stature ratio in Santals (15.58% vs. 15.21%, $p=0.000$). The observed difference in forearm length between these two ethnic groups aligns with the thermoregulatory (Allen's rule) hypothesis, which predicts that populations originating from warmer climates tend to have longer extremities relative to body size to facilitate heat dissipation [14,15]. Santals, as an indigenous group with long-standing residence in the tropical environment of northern Bangladesh, may have developed longer forearms as an adaptive trait [13,16]. In contrast, the Bangali population, though also residing in a warm climate, may have different genetic origins or admixture patterns that influence limb proportions [17]. The forearm-stature ratio of 15.58% in Santals is higher than that reported in several other populations. Comparative data show that Egyptian males have a ratio of approximately 15.35% [5], Iranian males 15.42% [6], and Korean males 14.98% [2]. The Santal ratio closely resembles that of tropical African populations, who typically exhibit longer limbs relative to stature [16,18]. This finding supports the hypothesis that Santals may retain ancestral limb proportion characteristics associated

with warm-climate adaptation [8,19]. The significantly lower multiplication factor in Santals (6.43 vs. 6.58, $p=0.000$) provides additional confirmation that forearms are longer relative to stature in this group. The multiplication factor, being the inverse of the forearm-stature ratio, offers a simple yet robust method for ethnic comparison without requiring complex statistical transformation [3,20]. This parameter could be particularly useful in field settings where rapid ethnic assessment is needed [21]. The correlation analysis revealed moderate positive correlations between forearm length and stature in both groups ($R=0.664$ for Santals, $R=0.547$ for Bangalis). These values are consistent with published literature, where correlation coefficients typically range from 0.55 to 0.75 across different populations [6,22]. The stronger correlation observed in Santals suggests that forearm length may be a more reliable stature predictor in this ethnically homogeneous group compared to the more diverse Bangali population [3,23]. The discriminatory accuracy analysis demonstrated that forearm length alone, using a cutoff value of 25.1 cm, correctly classified 62% of Santals and 58% of Bangalis, with an overall accuracy of 60%. While these values are moderate, they indicate that forearm length cannot be used as a standalone ethnic classifier but can serve as a supportive tool in conjunction with other anthropometric parameters [1,11]. The sensitivity and specificity values varied with different cutoff points, suggesting that the optimal threshold depends on the specific forensic or anthropological context [24]. The

percentile distribution data revealed that at the 50th percentile (median), Santals had a forearm length of 25.3 cm compared to 24.9 cm in Bangalis. This 0.4 cm difference at the median level reinforces the consistency of the ethnic difference across the entire distribution [15,19]. The 10th to 90th percentile ranges show minimal overlap between groups, further supporting the discriminatory potential of this measurement [20]. The findings of this study have practical implications. In forensic anthropology, where identifying unknown remains is crucial, forearm length measurements can contribute to ethnic assessment when used alongside other skeletal features [3,25]. In clinical medicine, population-specific reference standards for limb proportions are essential for evaluating growth and development abnormalities [2,9]. The absence of such standards for indigenous populations like Santals has been a significant gap [13,21]. Several mechanisms may explain the observed ethnic difference. Genetic factors likely play a primary role, as limb proportions are known to have high heritability [11,21]. Environmental factors, including nutrition and physical activity during growth, may also contribute [15]. Both groups in this study shared similar occupational backgrounds (day laborers or farmers), suggesting that socioeconomic and activity-related factors were reasonably controlled [12,18].

LIMITATIONS

This study was limited to adult males from a single district in Bangladesh, excluding females and other age groups. The findings may not generalize to Santal and Bangali populations residing in other regions or across different socioeconomic strata.

CONCLUSION

Forearm length significantly discriminates between adult male Santals and Bangalis. Santals possess longer forearms relative to stature, as evidenced by a higher forearm-stature ratio and lower multiplication factor ($p < 0.001$). This ethnic difference supports thermoregulatory adaptation and has practical applications in forensic anthropology. Population-specific reference standards for forearm length are recommended for accurate ethnic assessment in Bangladesh.

RECOMMENDATION

Future multi-center studies across different districts of Bangladesh are recommended, including females and diverse age groups. Development of population-specific regression equations and validation of cutoff values for forearm length as an ethnic discriminator in forensic contexts is strongly advised.

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